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THE CLOUD IS THE DATA REVOLUTION

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ABSTRACT:

Show the technological advance, created by MICROSOFT, by Bill Gates, through his own creation, as well as his programs of: a) Operating System, b) Word (for use in texts), Excel (for use in spreadsheets), Power Point (for use in presentations) and Access (for use in Databases and research, based on past information), notably in the latter. From there begins a new System Similar to Access that uses Access (from Microsoft) in order to compile information from past data that comes with futuristic, technological, financial, probabilistic, mathematical ideas of scientific projections, with a view to a new world, called Metaverse, today understood as the Cloud (where all Access (Microsoft) information, prepared by Google, is stored, plus the use of John McCarthy's thesis.